

FAILURE MECHANISMS IN ULTRAHIGH MODULUS POLYETHYLENE FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

We have studied the mechanical behavior and failure modes of six types of ultrahigh modulus polyethylene (UHMPE) fiber reinforced composites subjected to tension, compression, flexure and short-beam shear on an universal testing machine and in a scanning electron microscope. The results show that while the axial tensile properties of the unidirectional composites are excellent, the transverse tensile, axial compression and shear properties are not ideal, and the flexural performance lies in between. Under axial tension or flexure the composite fails in a ductile manner, with fiber pullout and breakage. Under transverse tension the dominant failure mode is the separation of fibers from the matrix while under axial compression fiber buckling and interface debonding are important. The primary failure mechanism in short-beam shear experiments is interlaminar shear, with the failure occurring in the middle layer where the shear stress is a maximum.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ultrahigh modulus polyethylene (UHMPE) fiber reinforced composites have attracted considerable attention in recent years because these materials have high specific strength and modulus, excellent impact and abrasive resistance, and good dielectric properties. The basic mechanical properties⁽¹⁻³⁾ and the effects of fiber surface treatment^(4,5) on these properties have been studied. However, there have been very few reports on the microscopic failure mechanisms of this class of materials. The present work aims to investigate the mechanical behavior and damage mechanisms of UHMPE fiber reinforced composites under tensile, flexural, interlaminar shear or compressive loading. By performing the experiments in a scanning electron microscope the damage process of the microstructure can be monitored as a function of time, thereby revealing the failure mechanisms.

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2. SAMPLE PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Composites comprising unidirectional or woven fabric of Spectra 1000 (S1000) polyethylene fibers and low density polyethylene (LDPE) or epoxy (EP) matrix were supplied by Allied-Signal Inc. To study the effects of fiber surface treatment some S1000 fibers were immersed in chromic acid and unidirectional composites incorporating untreated or treated fibers (TS1000) were prepared in our laboratory. The epoxy matrix (MEP) used is based on diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A and has a low curing temperature of 125°C. Table 1 shows the six types of samples studied in the present work. These samples were cut by a high-speed water jet containing emery powder.

Tensile, flexural, short-beam shear and compression experiments were performed on a Instron 1195 universal material tester. Transverse tensile, short-beam shear and compression measurements were also carried out on a Hitachi S570 scanning electron microscope. In these experiments the load-displacement curves were obtained and the dynamic failure processes were observed and photographed.

3. TENSILE FAILURE

As shown in Table 1 the axial tensile properties of the unidirectional composites are excellent because they are largely determined by the superior tensile performance of the fibers. The axial tensile strength and modulus of the sample with surface-treated fibers have values of 1.01 and 48 GPa, respectively.

Under axial tensile loading the unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite exhibits ductile complex fracture behavior. There are interface debonding, fiber pullout (Figure 1) and fiber breakage (Figure 2). After breakage the tip of the fiber exhibits large plastic deformation and has a spiral shape. A magnified picture of the tip of a broken fiber is shown in Fig. 3. Figure 4 shows that microfibrils are torn from the fiber. Figure 5 shows that the fiber splits longitudinally and fibrillates after tensile failure of the composite.

Fig. 1 Scanning electron micrograph showing UHMPE fibres pulled out from the LDPE matrix

Fig. 2 SEM micrograph showing the ductile fracture of UHMPE fibers

Fig. 3 SEM micrograph showing the tip of a broken UHMPE fiber

Fig. 4 SEM micrograph showing microfibrils torn from a UHMPE fiber

Fig. 5 Fibrillation of a UHMPE fiber after tensile failure of a unidirectional composite

Fig. 6 Interface debonding in unidirectional S1000/LDPE composites under transverse tension

The transverse tensile strength of the unidirectional composites is rather low (see Table 1). This is because the fiber surface is quite inert and has poor wetting property, thereby leading to poor interfacial adhesion. The transverse tensile strength of unidirectional S1000/LDPE composites with 53% and 73% fibers are 6.7 MPa and 5.6 MPa, respectively, which are even lower than the tensile strength (8.6 MPa) of the LDPE matrix. Figure 6 shows that the poor interfacial adhesion leads to the debonding of the fibers and the matrix. There is very little matrix material sticking to the fibers.

4. INTERLAMINAR SHEAR FAILURE

For unidirectional composites the short-beam shear strength τ_{ILSS} reflects the interlaminar shear properties and also the adhesion strength of the fiber/matrix interface. One of the weaknesses of UHMPE fiber composites is its low τ_{ILSS} and we attempt to improve the interface behavior by surface treatment of the fibers. As seen from Table 1 the τ_{ILSS} value of the epoxy matrix composite containing fibers treated with chromic acid is higher than that of the composite with untreated fibers by a factor of 2.4. Figures 7 - 10 show the damage processes occurring during the short-beam shear experiment. When the sample is deformed to a certain extent a stress whitening band is observed along the loading direction of the compression pin (Figure 7). With increasing loading shear damage of the matrix occurs in the compressed region. At a critical stress the sample fails. A shear damage band (Figure 8) is observed in the middle layer where the shear stress is a maximum. Failure first occurs at the fiber/matrix interface, then the crack propagates from the middle layer at an angle of 45°. The 45° cracks within the middle layer join together to form a continuous shear crack. Figure 9 shows the magnified picture of a region with quasi-continuous cracks. In the compressed region along the loading direction, shear cracks and compressive failure occur simultaneously and the shear microcracks join together to form large cracks. Figure 10 shows the interlaminar damage, the major mechanism being shear failure in the middle layer, together with bearing failure of the matrix near the loading zone.

Fig. 7 SEM micrograph showing a stress whitening band along the direction of loading in short-beam shear experiment on unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite

Fig. 8 SEM micrograph revealing the interlaminar shear failure surface in the middle layer of unidirectional S1000/LDPE composites

Fig. 9 Quasi-continuous interlaminar shear cracks in unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite

Fig. 10 SEM micrograph showing shear failure at the fiber/matrix interface of unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite

5. FLEXURAL FAILURE

The flexural strength is higher for the unidirectional composites than the composites with woven fabric. For the unidirectional S1000/MEP composites, fiber surface treatment leads to a slight (20%) increase in flexural strength. This arises because the improved adhesion leads to a stronger constraint on the matrix, thereby reducing the damage. As a result of the poor compressive properties of UHMPE fibers the flexural strength of unidirectional S1000/MEP composites is rather low, being only 1/7 of the axial tensile strength. This is contrary to the case of composites containing other high-performance fibers (such as carbon fibers) where these two parameters have similar values. Under a bending moment failure occurs first in the outermost layer. Each layer fails in turn until finally the sample cracks in a ductile manner. Figure 11 shows the complex failure modes including fiber pullout and fiber breakage. From the fracture surface (Figure 12) the bending of the fibers and damage of the LDPE matrix can be easily seen. In flexural measurements the major damage occurs in the layers under tension and secondary compressive damage of the matrix occurs near the loading pin.

Fig. 11 SEM micrograph showing the pullout and breakage of fibers in unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite after flexural failure

Fig. 12 Fracture surface of unidirectional S1000/LDPE composite after flexural failure

6. COMPRESSIVE FAILURE

The axial compressive strength of unidirectional S1000/MEP is 79 MPa, which is much lower than the axial tensile strength (985 MPa). This arises from the poor compressive properties of the fibers and is one of the major disadvantages of these composites. Improvement can be achieved by hybridization with carbon fibers ⁽⁶⁾. The compressive strength of the woven fabric reinforced composites is slightly lower than that of the unidirectional composite. Figures 13 - 16 show the microstructural features in woven fabric S1000/EP composites during compressive loading. Compression induces transverse tension that leads to interface debonding and shear yielding of the matrix between the knitted squares and between the fabrics. Without the support of the matrix the fibers buckle and then break (Figure 14). Local damage of the epoxy matrix and interface debonding occur (Figure 15). Finally main cracks are formed and the sample fails (Figure 16). The important failure mechanisms in this type of composites are microbuckling of fibers and interface separation.

Fig. 13 Original appearance of woven fabric S1000/EP composite

Fig. 14 SEM micrograph showing fiber microbuckling and interface separation in woven fabric S1000/EP composite under compression

Fig. 15 SEM micrograph showing shear yielding and cracking of the matrix in woven fabric S1000/EP composite under compression

Fig. 16 SEM micrograph showing the formation of a long crack in woven fabric S1000/EP composite under compression and the imprints left on the epoxy matrix by the debonded fibers

7. CONCLUSION

Upon loading UHMPE fiber reinforced composites generally exhibit ductile fracture. The failure mechanisms under various loading conditions can be elucidated by observing the dynamic fracture processes of the microstructure on a scanning electron microscope.

Ductile fracture is observed in axial tension or bending. There are fiber pullout and fiber breakage. Under a bending moment the outermost layer fails first because it is subjected to a strong tensile force. Many bent fibers are observed on the fracture surface. The flexural strength of the unidirectional composites is only about 15% of the axial tensile strength. This is because the flexural strength depends on the properties of the matrix and the compressive strength of the composite which is quite low.

Transverse tensile failure results from the debonding of the fibers and the matrix, while the damage processes in axial compression include fiber buckling and interface debonding. Interlaminar shear damage is the major process in short-beam shear measurements. This occurs at the interface of the middle layer since it is subjected to the highest shear stress. Compressive damage is also observed near the loading zone.

The damage mechanisms UHMPE fiber reinforced composites are different from those of composite materials containing brittle fibers (such as carbon fibers). Because of the poor fiber/matrix adhesion in UHMPE fiber composites the fibers are easily separated from the matrix. Almost no resin adheres to the fiber surface. Hence the major failure modes are fiber pullout and bending. Moreover, because the adhesion strength at the interface is lower than the strength of the matrix, the shear damage of the matrix is less severe than that of conventional composite materials.

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Table 1: Mechanical Properties of Different Types of Ultrahigh Modulus Polyethylene Fiber Reinforced Composites

Specimen	Axial Tensile		Transverse Tensile		Flexural Strength σ_{f1} (MPa)	Short Beam Shear Strength τ_{RBS} (MPa)	Axial Compressive Strength σ_{c1} (MPa)
	Strength σ_{t1} (MPa)	Modulus E_{t1} (GPa)	Strength σ_{t2} (MPa)	Modulus E_{t2} (GPa)			
LDPE	8.55	0.40	8.55	0.40		1.79	
1. S1000/LDPE [0] $V_f = 0.53$			6.67	0.55		6.52	
2. S1000/LDPE [0] $V_f = 0.73$			5.57	0.73		7.23	
3. S1000/MEP [0] $V_f = 0.60$	985	50.0			124	6.4	79.0
4. TS1000/MEP [0] $V_f = 0.60$	1012	48.0			150	15.6	
5. S1000/LDPE Woven $V_f = 0.80$	476	13.0			75.0	7.13	75.0
6. S1000/EP Woven $V_f = 0.80$					38.5	2.87	67.2

LDPE : Low Density Polyethylene, S1000 : Spectra 1000 Ultrahigh Modulus Polyethylene Fiber, EP : Epoxy, MEP : Epoxy Based on Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A.